

WP9

Technology and Science Watch

ISBE WP9 REPORT

D 9.7

**Report on the future needs with respect to storage
and hardware**

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Project ref. no.	INFRA-2012-2.2.4: 312455
Project title	ISBE – Infrastructure for Systems Biology Europe
	R= Report
Contractual date of	Month 18
Actual date of	Month 18
Deliverable number	D9.7
Deliverable title	Report on the future needs with respect to storage and hardware
Dissemination Level	PU
Status & version	Version 4
Number of pages	15
WP relevant to	WP9
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Nature of Deliverable: P= Prototype, R= Report, D=Demonstrator, O = Other.

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II. INTRODUCTION

During the preparatory phase the infrastructure needs to get an estimate of the state of the art with respect to existing and emerging technologies to formulate a technology vision for the operational phase of the infrastructure before starting its actual operation. One of the objectives of WP9 in collaboration with WP2 and WP4 is **Identification of the future needs of the systems biology community with respect to storage and hardware.**

In the initial period of the ISBE preparatory phase the reports on the future needs with respect to storage and hardware might serve as a guide for building up the infrastructure and give answers to several key questions: what we should watch in storage and hardware area and what is important for systems biology community, and how we can use it for ISBE infrastructure.

The first report does not aim to provide fully representative data covering all fields of storage and hardware area, but rather identify demands coming from the community towards the infrastructure and identify the existing state-of-the-art with respect to storage and hardware and show possible future directions in the usage of storage and hardware in systems biology community. Systems biology research needs collection and processing of data from large numbers of biological experiments using automated procedures and requires the ability to obtain, integrate and analyse complex data sets from multiple experimental sources using interdisciplinary tools. The hardware and data storage play the key role in this process.

OBJECTIVES

- Examining and evaluating of the existing state-of-the-art of storage and hardware in Life sciences
- Demands of systems biology community on ISBE hardware and storage

III. THE REPORT

This report represents the essence from tech literature watch, gathering information from the systems biology community and data storage and management facilities, a series of surveys and reports, data gained from BIO –IT World Survey and ISBE Wide survey, and by assembling statistical data of systems biology conference proceedings and abstracts.

A. 2013 LIFE SCIENCES IT SURVEY

It is essential to diagnose key trends in the life sciences IT space to be able to determine software and hardware usage in the future by systems biology community. In the survey which was conducted by Bio-IT World / Cambridge Healthtech Media Group we can find these trends thanks to responses from 121 senior executives, key opinion leaders in the industry, in life sciences IT – CIOs and VPs – from a larger sample of 200 respondents. (60% of respondents herein are CIOs, the remainder VPs or senior VPs of IT.)

Just under half the respondents work in biotech or pharma, the remainder work

How many other corporate locations will share/access your data both inside and outside your organization?

Bio-IT World survey

How would you best describe your organization?

Bio-IT World survey

in government, hospital, academia, or vendor organizations.

The survey reports a robust trend for IT investment: 45% expect their IT budgets to increase this year, whereas only 8% anticipate a decrease. Two thirds of respondents are planning increases of 6-15%, while 20% expect even higher increases in spending. Even so, more than 60% said that budget constraints form the biggest challenge for

1. CLOUD COMPUTING

Cloud computing was the most highly cited area for IT spending in 2013, being highlighted by a small majority of respondents. Other key areas include security, workflow technologies, and mobile technologies. One quarter of respondents said social media was a priority area for 2013.

In terms of the cloud, two thirds of respondents spend thousands a month on cloud storage, with 12% reporting expenditures greater than \$25,000/month.

Specific challenges include data storage, security, and staffing levels.

Which of the following do you see is the biggest benefit with migrating to the cloud?

Which of the following is your organization currently using for their cloud based platforms?

Bio-IT World survey

Bio-IT World survey

Roughly equal numbers (25-30%) reported using public clouds vs private clouds vs a hybrid cloud platform strategy.

How much of your storage is internal versus cloud based storage?

Bio-IT World survey

While some 30% respondents reported using Amazon Web Services for their public cloud platform, the report details a long list of other vendor suppliers for cloud and in-house storage platforms.

What vendors do you use for storage?

The most popular cloud application is email, but others scoring highly include Intranet and CRM. Nearly two thirds of respondents believe that all their IT platforms will be cloud-based within five years.

If using a public cloud solution, which are you currently using?

If using an on-premise/private cloud solution, which are you currently using?

2. DATA STORAGE

In terms of data storage, one quarter of respondents are already in the Petabyte storage range, with 7.5% storing more than 10 PB data. Fully 90% respondents expected their data repositories to grow in 2013.

What is your data storage capacity?

B. ISBE WIDE SURVEY

In order to ensure that ISBE meets the requirements of future systems biologists we are in the process of seeking opinion from key stakeholders in systems biology and related fields. By January 16, 2014 121 respondents have completed the online questionnaire (<http://project.isbe.eu/>) and let us know their views on the development of ISBE. In this report we concentrate on the answers related to future needs with respect to storage and hardware.

1. UNPUBLISHED DATA STORAGE

More than 76% of respondents store their **unpublished data** local to their group, 44% local to institution 20% cloud-based storage, 25% in a project or programme-wide repository, more than 14% in a community resource. The main reason why most respondents store their unpublished data local to group seem to be the fact it is simply for respondents the most comfortable way of storage, in-house, safe and cheap.

Q16 Where do you store your unpublished data (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 84 Skipped: 37

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014

We can identify ISBE **cloud-base**

storage as a potential storage tool in the future. However, it will be necessary to analyse this in detail with respect to ISBE storage and hardware future needs.

2. EXPERIENCED DIFFICULTIES IN MANAGING DATA

Q17 What difficulties have you experienced in managing your data (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 77 Skipped: 44

More than 48% of respondents have experienced **difficulties in managing their data** with storage space. More than 46% have experienced problems with transfer of data. More than 59% have difficulties with long-term storage and 40% with Linking data and models and Retrieval of data (24%).

What we can identify as potential area that is not provided in sufficient amount by home institutions or brings

difficulties for respondents and could be taken care of by the infrastructure are: **Long-term storage (59%), Back up of data (almost 52%)** with **Standards and curation (almost 52%)** which should be monitored in the near future and might be worth to deal with in the infrastructure.

3. PUBLIC REPOSITORIES USED FOR PUBLISHED DATA STORAGE

With respect to submitting **data to public repositories by respondents when is work published** it seems that **GEO (36%)** and **Array Express (more than 28%)** are the repositories which are mostly used by respondents. They also use PRIDE (more than 11%), European Nucleotide Archive (more than 10%), , PDB (more than 10%, PDB Europe 2.6%), PeptideAtlas (9%) and Metabolights (more than 6%) to submit their published data to public repositories. **About 19% do not use any public repositories to submit their data** which we can identify as a potential

Q19 Which public repositories do you submit your data to when your work is published (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 77 Skipped: 44

area of ISBE interest. There are several other repositories which are used by a few respondents: IntAct and SABIO-RK (2%), Electron Microscopy Data Bank – EMDB (1%) and Bio Dare(1%).

4. PUBLIC REPOSITORIES USED FOR MODELS STORAGE

With respect to **public repositories to submit models** it seems that **BioModels Database** (almost 30%) is the public repository which is used by most respondents. About 8% of respondents use JWS Online Repository and more than 5% use CellML public repositories to submit their models. More than 17% do not produce any models.

What we can identify as potential interest of ISBE infrastructure and should be analysed is the fact that more than 48% of respondents do not use any public repositories to submit their models. The reasons for this need to be understood and might open the question if the infrastructure should interface this in the future.

Q20 Which public repositories do you submit your models to when your work is published (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 74 Skipped: 47

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014

5. FORMATS USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA

SBML - Systems Biology Mark-up Language is a format used by more than 55% respondents for structuring and annotating their data and models. Respondents also use SAM/BAM - Sequence Alignment Map Format (15%), SBGN - Systems Biology Graphical Notation (about 13%), MAGE-ML - Microarray Gene Expression Mark-up Language (more than 11%), CellML - Cell Markup-Language (almost 9%), MAGE-TAB Microarray Gene Expression Tabular Format, MzML - Mass Spectrometry Mark-up Language and BED Format (all almost 8%), SED-ML - Simulation Experiments Mark-up Language (more than 6%), GFF – General feature Format (5%), SBRML - Systems Biology Results Mark-up Language (almost 4%). **SBML** seems to play the key role for respondents for structuring and annotating data and models.

Q21 What formats do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 78 Skipped: 43

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014

6. METADATA STANDARDS USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA

MIAME - Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment is a metadata standard used by more than 34% respondents for structuring and annotating their data and models. There are other metadata standards used by respondents:

MIRIAM - Minimal Information Required In the Annotation of biochemical Models (16%), MIAPE - Minimum Information About a Proteomics Experiment (9%), MIASE - Minimum Information About a Simulation Experiment (8%) and MIARE - Minimum Information About a RNAi Experiment (more than 6%), ISA - Investigations Studies Assays (4%), MIMIx - Minimum Information about a Molecular Interaction Experiment (more than 2%), MINSEQE - Minimal Information about a high throughput SEQUencing Experiment (more than 2%) used by respondents. **More than 52% do not use any metadata**

Q22 Which metadata standards do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 75 Skipped: 46

ISBE Wide Survey January 2014

standards for structuring and annotating their data and models. It is worth to analyse this in the near future.

7. ONTOLOGIES/VOCABULARIES USED FOR STRUCTURING AND ANNOTATING DATA

More than 57% of respondents use **GO - Gene Ontology** for structuring and annotating their data. SBO - Systems Biology Ontology is used by more than 18%, BioPax - Biological Pathways Ontology (almost 13%), MGED - Microarray and Gene Expression Data Ontology (almost 13%). More than 6% use PSI-MS - Mass Spectrometry Ontology and more than 6% use PSI-MI - Protein Interaction Ontology. CHEBI - Chemical Entities of Biological Interest is used by more than 6% as well. PSI_MOD - Protein Modification Ontology is used by more than 5% of respondents. More than 5% of respondents use MESH - Medical Subject Headings, more than 3% PATO - Phenotypic Quality Ontology. **More than 29% do not use any vocabularies/ontologies for structuring and annotating their data and models.**

Q23 Which ontologies/vocabularies do you use for structuring and annotating your data and models (please tick all that apply)?

Answered: 77 Skipped: 44

IV. CURRENT DEMANDS FOR ISBE INFRASTRUCTURE WITH RESPECT TO STORAGE AND HARDWARE

Due to the fundamental role of IT services in today's research, ISBE infrastructure in compliance with e-IRG White Paper 2013 conclusion should become a high-quality, accessible to all researchers throughout Europe and supplying integrated IT services (storage and hardware) according to the different requirements of the various user research areas.

However, researchers are increasingly interested in integrated services focused on their own problems, and much less in who delivers these services. Ultimately, researchers and infrastructure users look for user-friendly access to all infrastructure services they might need and which should be simple to use and not costly to manage. With the scope of increasing importance of international research collaboration and the use of data, ISBE should reflect this need which is becoming more important.

Such ISBE infrastructure with respect to storage and hardware services should include:

- access to **high-performance computing** (supercomputing) and high-throughput computing (including grid computing)
- access to **high end storage for ever increasingly large data sets**
- advanced **networking services** to connect computing and storage resources to users and instruments;
- **middleware components** to enable the seamless use of the above services, including authentication and authorisation;
- deal with **large datasets** and large data rates from the experiments
- ensuring better **curation of data**, including improved use of effective automated curation technologies;
- access to **models** and their storage
- **semantic web technologies** for systems biology data and tools.
- enable easy and standardised **metadata**
- allow transparent and secure remote **access** to data
- provide unique and persistent **authentication** to all users
- allow long-term **preservation** of data
- provide compatible open source data **analysis** software
- allow overall **interoperation** through common standard schemes,
- provide a **common data policy**

As a living ecosystem, ISBE infrastructure must be flexible and able to change fast in accordance with the needs of users. ISBE should provide services which are better than what commercial providers can offer, or at least at the same level but cheaper.

According to the e-IRG 2012 “Blue Paper” on Data Management the growing importance of data available everywhere and at every stage of research is causing a rapid increase in the amount of data available and the capacity needed for its storage. The amount of data will increase by a factor of 61 over the next 10 years (source - *The 2011 IDC Digital Universe Study*). The amount of data is estimated to exceed the size of available infrastructure resources on which data can be stored by 60% (*The 2011 IDC Digital Universe Study*). For some areas, such as DNA sequencing, the estimate increase far exceeds this: the volume of public DNA sequence data doubles around every 9 months currently. This doubling time is substantially more than disk or CPU doubling times.

That is why **Big Data management** and **Cloud computing** can be seen as the challenging items in the near future and are worth to analyse them with respect to ISBE future needs. To cope with **Big data** - a collection of data sets so large and complex that it becomes difficult to process using on-hand database management tools or traditional data processing applications - new tools and methods are being developed, such as Hadoop and NoSQL data stores. Hadoop provides the necessary tools for several Big Data methods such as association rule learning, cluster analysis, pattern recognition, predictive modelling, and others. NoSQL data stores allow for data to be partitioned across different machines, as there is no need to follow a fixed relational schema. **The “cloud”** is not a separate infrastructure, but a range of services, which can be implemented on existing e-Infrastructures. Even though Cloud computing was the most highly cited area for IT spending in 2013 (Bio IT World Survey), it is not yet clear if the cloud is the best solution for scientific computing and storage of scientific data.

V. CONCLUSION

The systems biology looks at very large systems and deals with the enormousness amount of data. To enable this, the data needs to be managed, stored and preserved in a cost-efficient way, with appropriate quality and safety assurances. It will also be necessary to deal with and set up the access to the data across borders and domain boundaries must be secured. We need tackle the problem on the different levels.

1. Data storage – computational projects in system biology produce huge amount of data, one project can produce several terabytes of the data that need to be stored for the long term. Development should focus at the possibility to extend the current storage capacities and also to develop the completely new technologies of data storage.

2. Data transfer – due to the complexity of projects in systems biology, the many tasks of the same project are produced in different places. For the analysis of the data many different research group in different places have to share the data. The fast way of the sharing and transferring the large amount of data is needed. For some projects this process can currently occupy up to 10% of the project time.

3. Data processing – The analysis of the enormous amount of data requires huge processing power and can take the majority of the project time. We need to look at the improvement of the current CPU and GPU technologies as well as development of the new computational technologies. The development of the new computer architectures and the more effective algorithms would improve current situation.

4. Data generation – The many data for projects in system biology are generated during simulations. To improve this stage, not only improvement of the processing power is need, but we also need to improve fast storage of the temporary data. The improvement of the fast memory is extremely important. Also the development of the very fast way to store extremely large temporary data (up to 1TB) would be very beneficial.

VI. THE NEXT STEPS

The next steps are planned:

- (i) to identify ISBE cloud-based storage possibilities*
- (ii) to identify Limited integration with commercial hardware and storage providers*
- (iii) to enable access to existing data*
- (iv) to analyse Innovative developments in data-specific compression available and applicable for ISBE infrastructure*
- (v) to analyse big data management with respect to ISBE needs*
- (vi) to analyse data, Long-term storage, back up of data, Standards and curation ISBE possibilities*